

Dissemination and Communication Plan

Deliverable 5.1

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Lead partner: **ALPHA**

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Deliverable abstract	<p>Dissemination and communication plan is the main guideline for the execution of the dissemination & communication activities that will be carried out within the OVERWATCH projects. It gives an overview of the whole dissemination and communication activities foreseen throughout the project.</p> <p>The plan defines the dissemination objectives, the target audiences, the key messages, the dissemination channels to be used, the promotional materials as well as the timeline of their use. Also, the plan presents the methodology of performing the dissemination activities. It also sets some achievement indicators to evaluate the effectiveness and success of these activities.</p> <p>Finally, this plan is conducted to achieve the maximum impact and support the exploitation activities.</p>
Keywords	Dissemination and communication plan, Communication strategy, stakeholder engagement

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¹ Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

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Abbreviations

AR	Augmented Reality
D	Deliverable
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
EC	European Commission
EGNSS	European Global Navigation Satellite System
EMS	Emergency Management System
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
H2020	Horizon 2020
HE	Horizon Europe
KPI	Key Performance Index
OA	Open Access
R&D	Research and Development
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
U&S	Users and Stakeholders
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document is the D5.1 “Dissemination and Communication Plan” (DCP) for OVERWATCH, foreseen in the frame of Task 5.1.

The main objective of this document is to provide the guidelines for the promotion activities to be carried out by the OVERWATCH Consortium throughout the whole duration of the project.

To achieve such objective, the document provides the approach that will be used to maximize impact by identifying key promotion audiences, outlining the types of actions together with the role of OVERWATCH Consortium partners in the set of activities foreseen in this DCP.

Thus, a promotion strategy has been designed and set in place targeting dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. The different activities and actions are described in detail in section 3, while the table below is providing an overview of the overall strategy.

Type of Action	Objective	Description	Activities
Dissemination actions for awareness	Set of activities aimed at promoting the project activities and results towards stakeholders and aimed at improving awareness of users on the project and the development of the technologies.	The majority of these actions start immediately after preliminary results and after the conclusions of WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4. They are connected with the project outcomes (e.g., press outcomes on OVERWATCH technologies). The dissemination actions aimed at improving U&S awareness should be considered the most relevant activities for the project, given it is important to make U&S aware of how the proposed technologies work and how the final product could benefit from them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logo • Website • Project brochures • Press releases and publications • National and international conferences and events • Trainings • Newsletter
Dissemination actions for U&S involvement	Engagement and involvement of relevant users and stakeholders in different phases of the project in relation to the different objectives and activities.	This type of action starts early in the project and could last until the end of the project. It is strictly connected with specific WPs and/or Task objectives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update regularly the contact database • Workshops • In-field demonstration • Clustering activities

Exploitation	Activities aimed at the market uptake of the proposed solution.	This type of action is linked to the last part of project activities aimed at commercial exploitation of the project results.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project exploitation • Monitor and Interface with similar projects • Synergies
Communication	Additional actions to communicate the project results not only to the main stakeholders, end-users or scientific community but also to the general public.	Communication actions through a plethora of media e.g., website and social media channels, magazines and press.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploitation of the website for promotion and other activities • Publication of audio-visual material • Social media publications • Other communication channels

Overview of OVERWATCH audiences, activities and outputs

Moreover, the activities' outputs foreseen can be segmented according to the frequency of release (i.e., how often they are released); and target audience (which target audiences are addressed).

In this context, the dissemination activities represent the core part of the overall strategy, given the innovative solution proposed by OVERWATCH and its final products stemming from the R&D are currently not known for most U&S. Hence, the website, publication on relevant sector journals and the participation to international conferences and events are the key channels.

Also, the exploitation of results is of a great importance for the market awareness and further adoption of final solution. Moreover, specific communication actions are foreseen in order to reach a wider audience, when relevant and possible. Nevertheless, these actions play a secondary role in the overall OVERWATCH promotion scheme, considering the scope of the project, mostly related to professionals more than mass market target audience.

For all previously mentioned activities, gender-neutral and gender-sensitive language is predefined and a gender specific action plan related to communication and dissemination has been set in place. This allows to ensure that the gender dimension is integrated as a transversal issue in the OVERWATCH project activities.

Finally, as a result from all DCP activities, the project' achievements and outcomes activities are foreseen to go beyond the lifetime of the project reaching wide audiences and promoting the market uptake of the developed solutions. To measure the expected results of DCP, they have been outlined and presented in section 4 in terms of goals and key performance indicators (KPIs), brief overview can be seen in table below. An update of the DCP proposed actions with a KPIs progress report will be performed in D.5.2 "Report on Dissemination and Communication activities", planned for M18.

Item	Goal	Quantity	KPI
Logo	Diffusion to the widest audience	1	Logo ready
Website	Create a user-friendly website	1	50 000+ visits updated regularly
Project brochure	To reach large audience	2+	200+ readers
Press references	Diffusion to widest audience by general non-scientific means by Consortium	20+	1 000+ readers
Short video	Short video explaining key research outputs	10	5 000+ views
Demonstration video	Videos from demonstration	2	
Final video	Final video of the project with an overview of the product and results obtained	1	
International conferences and events	Participation to a key event and publication to peer-reviewed scientific journals	3+ presentations 5 journals 10 conference papers	200+ people per event
Trainings	Trainings for professionals during the project, mostly linked with technical application works performed at the case studies	2+	150 people
Newsletter	Engagement with target groups	6	1 every 6 months
Contact Database	Key Contact database	1	Updated regularly
Demonstration	Demonstration with advisory group, stakeholders and first responders	2 events In 2 different countries	25 + organisations involved
Clustering activities	Promotion of networks and active cluster with other H2020 European ongoing related projects, European and National Technology Platforms (e.g., CERIS)	3+	3+ EU organizations, clusters or working groups engaged for user needs definition and results dissemination
Synergies	Increase value and performance of the project (e.g., joint dissemination and synergy to support the technological evolution)	2+ 2+	2+ EGNOS initiatives 2+ H2020/HE projects
Social media	Spreading the project achievements to a wider audience	3 accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook) 300+ posts	5 000+ followers 10 000+ interactions

OVERWATCH Dissemination and Communication KPI's

1. Introduction

The following document is the “Dissemination and Communication Plan” conducted and organised by ALPHA, leader of Task 5.1 “Dissemination and Communication” for the OVERWATCH project. In the following text aims and objectives of the plan (chapter 1.1), relations to other activities in the project (chapter 1.2) and report structure (chapter 1.3) are presented.

1.1. Aims and objectives

Dissemination and communication are essential elements in any project. Dissemination presents sharing research results with potential users – peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers. Sharing research results with the rest of the scientific community, enriches the contribution to the progress of science. Communication presents the actions of the beneficiaries that promote actions and results, by providing target information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in a strategic and effective manner and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim of Dissemination and Communication is to ensure that the project objectives, activities and outcomes will reach the relevant target groups (such as Scientific, Industrial and Large audience) in and beyond the demonstrator and test campaign. Therefore, a dissemination and communication plan for OVERWATCH is developed.

The main objectives of this report are to:

- Describe the approach adopted to define the main project promotion actions aimed at addressing the different Users and Stakeholders (U&S) clusters identified.
- Set up and present the DCP for using and disseminating the knowledge in the context of the OVERWATCH project, through various means.
- Provide main conclusions, mainly in terms of expected results related to different promotion actions.

This DCP describes the plan made at the beginning of the project foreseen for the consortium as a whole for the dissemination of the project concepts and outcomes, according to the provisions of the Description of the Action (DoA), and the work foreseen under WP5 [RD01].

In addition, this document sometimes goes beyond the DoA in line with the promotion opportunities already emerged during the project or with some potential actions that the team will evaluate if useful and will undertake accordingly. In this sense, the document specifies the methodology to be followed for the design, implementation, coordination and monitoring of all project activities aiming at achieving not only the dissemination but more in general the promotion objectives of the OVERWATCH project. Also, it has set some achievement indicators to evaluate the effectiveness and the success of these activities.

1.2. Relations to other activities in the project

Spreading awareness of the project’s achievements to relevant audiences via dissemination/communication channels, reaching as many people/ organizations as possible and increasing project visibility, is the main aim of the Dissemination and Communication activity.

To achieve such objective all partners of the OVERWATCH consortium will be engaged to participate. Indeed, being a cross action, the dissemination and communication plan activities are interlinked with all the achievements of the project, at all of its stages of progress.

1.3. Report structure

The document is organised according to the following structure:

- Chapter 0 is the introduction with the description of the main aims and objectives of the Dissemination and Communication plan itself.
- Chapter 2 presents the approaches used to maximize the impact by means of identification of main users and stakeholders target groups, outlining the main identified actions and role of OVERWATCH partners.
- Chapter 3 is devoted to the OVERWATCH promotion strategy throughout dissemination, exploitation of results and communication including possible gender issues.
- Chapter 4 reports the main conclusions and expected results outlining the key achievements indicators.

2. The approach used to maximise impact

This section focuses on the approach designed to identify key promotion audiences, i.e., stakeholders and users clustered in different target groups. In the following chapters main U&S target groups for the OVERWATCH project dissemination, exploitation and communication are identified (chapter 2.1), dissemination, exploitation, communication and related type of actions are presented (chapter 2.2), the role of the project's partners in relation to these actions (chapter 2.3) and the OVERWATCH dissemination and communication plan, enlarging its original scope with key insights on all main promotion actions (chapter 2.4) are presented.

2.1. Identification of main users and stakeholder target groups

For an effective realisation of each strategy, it is crucial to know who the subjects for the promotion are. For this reason, key audiences have been identified since the proposal stage of the project and these are the potential OVERWATCH U&S [RD01]. Moreover, the identified U&S are clustered in different target groups in order to engage and involve the key actors of the OVERWATCH value chain. For example, during the user needs and requirement definition U&S have been involved as presented in D1.1 "End-user Requirements" [RD02].

In general, target groups could be entities and/or individuals that can potentially benefit from the project results. As far as OVERWATCH project is concerned, the identified users and stakeholder clusters are presented in Table 1, grouped by the different areas of interest i.e., Policy Makers, Earth observation (EO) and European global navigation satellite system (EGNSS) programmes, Industry, Scientific community, Civilian Security. Last group of the stakeholders is identified as a potential end-user.

Target Audience	Description	Example of relevant bodies for OVERWATCH
Policy Makers	Local, National and international entities devoted to the disaster prevention and mitigation measures, that should be updated about the latest prevention and management methodologies and technological developments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governments/Institutions at European and International level • Agencies involved in the policy design • National Authorities • Local Authorities
EO and EGNSS Programmes	EO and EGNSS programmes devoted to the disaster monitoring, prevention and mitigation, that are interested in collaboration or use of the OVERWATCH outcomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copernicus • Galileo • EGNOS
Industry	Industry solution providers and companies involved in the emergency management, that are interested in collaboration or use of OVERWATCH outcomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency response solutions providers • Other potential industries • Insurance companies
Scientific community	Projects and researchers focused on the emergency management solutions available for collaboration/cooperation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universities • Research centres • NGOs working in emergency management development
Civilian Security	Potential end-users and pilot users; They are main actors in the emergency management phase, so they could be involved also in the project activities and project business development (e.g., market assessment, cost-benefit presentation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil protection • Fire fighter operation units • Regional and local authorities • NGOs working in emergency management development

Table 1 - Stakeholders identification for the dissemination activities

To reach the stakeholders, a coordinated approach has been set in place between the “Dissemination and communication” (Task T5.1) and the “International cooperation and synergies” (Task T5.3). The final aim for this cooperative activity is to reach all relevant stakeholders and decision makers, including national and international authorities, in order to make them aware about the project, its development and results. To achieve such a goal, various activities are being set in place, to maximise the visibility of the project throughout dissemination events (e.g., workshops, webinars, conferences). Significant contribution lies in the realization of the T5.3 task aimed to build networks among key stakeholders and, at the same time, raising interest and engage with those

stakeholders willing to get involved in implementing the OVERWATCH developed solutions in natural and cultural areas within their region of competence.

2.2. Dissemination, exploitation and communication type of actions

The European Commission (EC) sets a clear distinction among dissemination, exploitation and communication. These activities shape the core part of a comprehensive promotion system, but with three different scopes and objectives (see [RD03]):

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium. Disclosure may sound passive, like a shop opening up, but it is an activity, like a shopkeeper attracting customers. It is a process of promotion and awareness raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups (like research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, to enable them to use the results in their own work.

In line with the European Commission's (EC) definition, dissemination is considered here the set of actions aimed at increasing awareness and involving key user and stakeholder groups in a targeted way. Moreover, dissemination actions are considered mainly "one-way" actions, i.e., activities with few or specific feedbacks coming from the audience.

Exploitation is the use of the results in developing, creating and marketing or improving a product, process or service during and after the project's implementation. It can be for commercial purposes but also for improving policies, and for tackling economic and societal problems. Exploitation focuses on the actual use of the results, translating research concepts into concrete solutions that have a positive impact on the public's quality of life.

In line with the EC definition, exploitation of results is considered here the set of actions aimed at reaching key actors in the market, such as for example decision makers or European institutions, to foster the solution adoption (e.g., lobbying/networking activities). Actions presented in this document are complementary to those that will be reported in D5.5 "Exploitation Plan and first exploitation activities".

Communication means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how European Union (EU) funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

In line with the EC definition, communication is considered here the set of actions aimed at reaching the general public (and not only specific user groups) with traditional and new tools. Moreover, communication actions are considered mainly "two-way" actions, i.e., activities aimed at creating a flow of information, comments and exchange between Consortium and multitude of audiences and at encouraging discussion with general public (e.g., through social media).

Dissemination, exploitation of results and communication activities will be undertaken both at consortium and at partner's level, as a part of an overall strategy composed by four types of actions in relation to their objective. The different types of actions are described in detail in section 3, while in the Table 2 below shows a preliminary overview of the global strategy.

Type of Action	Objective	Description	Activities
Dissemination actions for awareness	Set of activities aimed at promoting the project activities and results towards stakeholders and aimed at improving awareness of users on the project and the development of the technologies.	The majority of these actions start immediately after preliminary results and after the conclusions of WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4. They are connected with the project outcomes (e.g., press outcomes on OVERWATCH technologies). The dissemination actions aimed at improving U&S awareness should be considered the most relevant activities for the project, given it is important to make U&S aware of how the proposed technologies work and how the final product could benefit from them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logo • Website • Project brochures • Press releases and publications • National and international conferences and events • Trainings • Newsletter
Dissemination actions for U&S involvement	Engagement and involvement of relevant users and stakeholders in different phases of the project in relation to the different objectives and activities.	This type of action starts early in the project and could last until the end of the project. It is strictly connected with specific WPs and/or Task objectives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update regularly the contact database • Workshops • In-field demonstration • Clustering activities
Exploitation	Activities aimed at the market uptake of the proposed solution.	This type of action is linked to the last part of project activities aimed at commercial exploitation of the project results.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project exploitation • Monitor and Interface with similar projects • Synergies
Communication	Additional actions to communicate the project results not only to the main stakeholders, end-users or scientific community but also to the general public.	Communication actions through a plethora of media e.g., website and social media channels, magazines and press.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploitation of the website for promotion and other activities • Publication of audio-visual material • Social media publications • Other communication channels

Table 2 - Overview of dissemination, exploitation and communication types of activities

As presented Figure 1, the activities listed above can be segmented according to:

- Frequency of release (i.e., how often they are published)
- Target audience (to which type of audience is addressed)

2.3. Role of OVERWATCH partners

The OVERWATCH consortium is composed of ten partners across five different countries (Poland, Germany, Italy, Portugal, Denmark), the consortium offers different but complementary expertise and relevant know-how to maximize the project impacts and results. In the paragraph below the role of each partner is presented.

2.3.1. Key supporting partners

The role of key supporting partners in terms of impact maximisation are presented in the following Table 3.

Partner	Role of partner in terms of impact maximisation	Dissemination	Exploitation	Communication
Partner responsible for action's coordination				
ALPHA	Expert in the overall business strategy and institutional communication and dissemination activities, in the frame of dissemination, communication and lobbying activities to the EC.	x		x
Partners involved for support and inputs				
ITHACA	Expert in engineering and operating added value services within the main project topic. Copernicus Emergency Management System (EMS) service provider, it is lead of the project service exploitation and has a strong link with the overall scientific community related to the main project topic. It will act as end-user exploiting the system and technological modules developed.	x	x	x
LINKS	Research institution with a strong link with the overall scientific community related to the main project topics. They can support the exploitation due to strong relationship with civil protection, disaster management and other industrial sectors.	x	x	x
ISQ	Entity with a wide experience in the activities of technical inspections, consultancy, testing, training and research can provide communication actions within their network of stakeholders and will contribute in the development of trainings. They can also support the exploitation due to strong relationship with civil protection, disaster management and other industrial sectors.	x	x	x
CBK	Space Research centre due to its role and connection with stakeholders and potential end users it can support the dissemination and communication activities. It will be in charge for the project's demonstration in Poland. They can also support the exploitation due to strong relationship with civil protection, disaster management and other industrial sectors.	x	x	x
ENGINEERING	Company with an extensive experience in building digital solutions. Its network of contacts and scientific community circles in topics related to the project can be leveraged for communication activities.	x	x*	x
ROBOTTO	Born as the solution for Emergency Management in collaboration with Danish Emergency Management Agency. Its network of contacts and scientific community circles in topics related to the project can be leveraged for communication activities.	x	x	x

2.4.1. Open access publications

It must be stressed that, in the frame of the dissemination and communication plan and foreseen related actions, Open Access (OA) is guaranteed to scientific publications resulting from the publicly funded project, in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013.

Indeed, as indicated in [RD01], the partners have committed themselves to provide OA to all scientific publications (free of charge online access for any user) using 'green' OA and 'gold' OA. Therefore, OVERWATCH will ensure open access to all peer-reviewed publications and seek it on other types of scientific publications, where project outcomes are published, using OpenAIRE compliant repository (i.e., Zenodo²). Specific budget has been considered for publishing the most important scientific papers using Open Access. It is envisaged that “gold” open access will be the preferred option, whereby the partners will publish in peer reviewed scientific journals that, already, are committed to solely open access methods or that can foresee (under payment) this option. The public technical reports and other communicative documents will be archived within the project website, in the repository section “Documents and reports”, with free access (“green” open access).

In this context, as the partners of the OVERWATCH consortium have envisaged a set of publications upon their work, an assessment of publications and publications intentions has been performed. To this end, an editorial **plan for the project’s publication has been drafted**.

The list of publications items is monitored and updated on a regular basis. This assures that the plan for publications respects the indicated timeline and allows to update the list of topics that are likeable to be published as a scientific paper. When these papers for publications are finalized and are finally public, they will be available through:

- OVERWATCH webpage, in the section OUTCOMES devoted to “publications”
- Social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook) with a devoted post/tweet
- OVERWATCH ResearchGate profiles (see also chapter 3.3.3)

Additionally, it is worth to note that when opportunities for publications arise, these are flagged from time to time by the communication team to the OVERWATCH Consortium in order to maximize the opportunities for publications of relevant papers related to the work and/or specific aspects that are being developed within the project.

2.4.2. Public deliverables

Deliverables with a public scope (i.e., public deliverables, conference papers, journals papers) will include their respective executive summaries, in order to bring out the most pertinent items for key stakeholders and, more in general, for the interested reader. As these summaries represent an additional dissemination tool, such executive summaries will be prepared in order to be easy to read and “user-friendly”, providing a snapshot of the key findings to assure maximum adoption by the relevant users.

Once approved, the OVERWATCH public deliverables will be available directly throughout the project’s website (see chapter 3.1.1.2) and social media channels (see chapter 3.3.3). When published, especially on the website, a brief description explaining the content of the document in a few lines will be provided.

² Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/>

Nevertheless, it is worth to note that as a general rule, the executive summaries are implemented in all OVERWATCH deliverables. Their “readability” will be verified in the procedures for the projects’ quality assurance, especially during the peer review process before the delivery.

3.OVERWATCH promotion strategy

This section outlines the specific OVERWATCH dissemination, results exploitation and communication approaches describing each of them according to the strategy and tools adopted. In the following chapters dissemination strategy with details on activities/tools (chapter 3.1), main inputs on exploitation strategy with activities/tools (chapter 3.2) and communication strategy with potential actions/tools (chapter 3.3) as well as gender issue in activities (chapter 3.4) are presented.

3.1. Dissemination

Dissemination actions are divided in two groups: (i) Dissemination actions for awareness (chapter 3.1.1) and (ii) Dissemination actions for user and stakeholder involvement (chapter 3.1.2).

3.1.1. Dissemination actions for awareness

The dissemination actions aimed at improving U&S awareness should be considered the most relevant activities for the project, given it is important to make U&S aware of how the proposed technologies work and how the final product could benefit from them. To achieve this, a set of actions described in the following chapters have been presented and they are Logo (chapter 3.1.1.1), Website (chapter 3.1.1.2), Project brochure (chapter 3.1.1.3), Press releases and publications (chapter 3.1.1.4), International conferences and events (chapter 3.1.1.5), Trainings (chapter 3.1.1.6) and Newsletters (chapter 3.1.1.7).

3.1.1.1. Logo

The OVERWATCH logo (see Figure 3) has been designed by ALPHA, and agreed with the Consortium, and delivered in the third month. The logo design, logotype, presents the project name with a focus on the first letter ‘O’ which represents the “terrain mapping” through a stylized depiction of the Earth. In addition to the Earth, the logo features a dot which represents a satellite or drone, emphasize the use of advanced technologies to gather data and map the terrain. The colour ‘PANTONE RED 032U - SOLID UNCOATED’, has been chosen accurately to highlight the sector of interest for the project. In general, the colour red, is associated with urgency, danger, crisis and warning. In addition, the payoff “*more than a map*” has been designed to emphasize the dissemination action communicating very briefly the project.

Figure 3 - OVERWATCH logo with payoff

3.1.1.2. Website

The OVERWATCH website, www.overwatchproject.eu, covers a pivotal role in the dissemination strategy. In fact, OVERWATCH team uses the website as a key channel to disseminate the overall project and all relevant results achieved. Moreover, the website will highlight all events where OVERWATCH will be present during the whole project time, maximising the project impact in terms of user and stakeholder interest and awareness.

The website design is clean and simple to communicate in the direct manner the content. The website contains the following pages:

- HOMEPAGE
- ABOUT
 - The Project
 - Earth observation
 - Augmented reality
 - Drones
 - Artificial intelligence
- PARTNERS
- OUTCOMES
- UPDATES
- CONTACT US

The **HOMEPAGE** contains six sections: i) brief introduction to the project (the textual content is followed with the background video), ii) four main project's technologies brief intro, iii) the project introduction video, iv) 'tell us who you are' section that shows a specific content according to the user typology, v) calendar bar with the upcoming events of the project's interest vi) partners brief presentation: slider with logos. The homepage has an interactive design, each section has clickable elements (buttons, icons, logos) to keep the user's attention and make them curious to find out more about the certain topic.

The **ABOUT** page is separated in five pages that can be selected from the drop-down menu. They can be divided in two big groups: Project and Technology.

The Project page contains four sections: i) project in a nutshell, ii) project's detailed description iii) four main project's technologies brief intro iv) calendar bar with the upcoming events of the project's interest.

The pages of four **Technologies** are all structured in the same way and they contain a first section with the detailed explanation of the technology and a second section with the benefits for a single technology. The Earth Observation, Drones and Artificial Intelligence pages have interactive visual example of the relative technology. The idea behind this approach is to transmit in an interactive and innovative way the technology used in the project.

The **PARTNERS** page can be divided in two main sections: i) summary of the consortium, ii) partners presentation with a dedicated section that shows the expertise and experiences in the project's sector.

The **OUTCOMES** page represents an overview of produced and delivered material during the project life. Each promotional material (e.g., deliverable, brochure, scientific publication etc) will be presented by title and brief description, followed by download button. In case of confidential documents, a summary of the content will be presented. The page will be updated monthly.

The **UPDATES** page contains two sections: i) calendar bar with the upcoming events of the project's interest ii) list of the past events with their short description and link to the more detailed source (pdf or webpage).

The **CONTACT US** page contains **the** contact form – all emails arrive to the contact@overwatchproject.eu email (managed by ALPHA).

All previously mentioned pages have fixed header and footer. The **HEADER** contains logo, pages menu (including the drop-down menu) and the languages (English, Portuguese and Polish). The **FOOTER** contains social media icons (with redirecting link to each social media page), Newsletter subscription, menu overview and details about the funding.

The website is setup to be multilingual and the content is available is English, Polish and Portuguese. In case the necessity for additional language arises during the project life, it can be easily added.

Figure 4 - OVERWATCH website

3.1.1.3. Project brochures

As foreseen in [RD01], specific project brochures will be prepared and translated to different languages. This will allow to support the overall project dissemination activities by providing information about the OVERWATCH objectives, achievements and expected results, and will be updated accordingly throughout the whole duration of the project.

A first brochure (Figure 5) is published on M6. The brochure is tri-fold A5 format. The idea behind this dissemination material is to explain in a short and simple way the project and foster the interest of the people inside and outside of the emergency management sector.

Figure 5 - Brochure outside and inside (preliminary version)

A second brochure is planned for the M25, to foster the exploitation of the results. However, in case of need for additional brochure arises during the project life, such materials can be created upon request.

In detail, the brochures will be available to the OVERWATCH Consortium partners for workshops, trainings, for participation at conferences and events, and they will also be available on the project’s website in the “OUTCOMES” section.

3.1.1.4. Press releases and publications

In view of the dissemination activity, OVERWATCH will target the production of high impact contributions to be disseminated through a peer-reviewed publication.

A list of scientific journals and e-publication magazines that are of particular relevance to the project topics is provided in Table 4. These represent possible venues where the OVERWATCH achievements may be published.

Journal name	Publisher	Impact factor
Int. J. of Disaster Risk Reduction, link	Elsevier	4.842
Int. J. of Disaster Risk Science, link	Springer	4.5
J. of Int. Crisis and Risk Communication Research, link	Nicholson School of Communication and Media	2.2
J. of Contingencies and Crisis Management, link	Wiley	3.42
Natural Hazards	Springer	3.158
Journal of Flood Risk Management	Blackwell Publishing	3.564
European Journal of Remote Sensing	Taylor & Francis	3.168

Table 4 - List of relevant open-access journals

It is important to point out that any other high-rated journal, special issue and magazine related to emergency management, risk reduction, flood and fire event management and solutions may be a proper venue to disseminate OVERWATCH results.

3.1.1.5. International conferences and events

OVERWATCH project presentation during relevant international conferences and events is considered a key dissemination channel to improve awareness on the developed solutions.

For this reason, dissemination activities will be conducted also through the participation to conferences, summits, exhibitions, seminars, workshops and other events related to the disaster management, risk management and mitigation domains. These are important opportunities in which the project outputs can be widespread to the proper audience.

A preliminary list of annual or biannual conferences/ events relevant for the project is provided in Table 5. The evaluation of effective participation will be made on an individual basis for each event.

Name	Date & frequency	Description	Link
Community of Users for Secure, Safe, Resilient Societies (CERIS)	Regularly held thematic events Frequent See calendar	Aiming to facilitate interactions within the security research community and users of research outputs, the Commission established the Community of Users for Safe, Secure and Resilient Societies (CoU), which gathered around 1,500 registered stakeholders (policy makers, end-users, academia, industry and civil society) and regularly held thematic events with the security research community. Named CERIS , the platform continues and expands the work of the CoU, in light of the forthcoming Horizon Europe developments between 2021-2027.	link
EENA Conference	Annual April 2023	EENA Conference & Exhibition focus on new technologies, informative and insightful sessions on a variety of topics impacting the sector, from emergency service staff to solutions providers.	link
European Geosciences Union Conference	Annual April 2023	The EGU aims to provide a forum where scientists, especially early career researchers, can present their work and discuss their ideas with experts in all fields of geoscience.	link
Information Systems for Crisis Response and Management (ISCRAM)	Annual May 2023	The ISCRAM promote R&D, exchange of knowledge and deployment of information systems for crisis management, including the social, technical and practical aspects of all information and communication systems used in all crisis phases.	link
Congress of the Italian Society of Remote Sensing	Annual June 2023	AIT , since its foundation in 1985, has been the key reference subject for supporting communication and coordination of scientific activities in the field of Earth Observation in Italy.	link
Int. Crisis Management conference (ICMC)	Annual June 2023	The ICMC conference is a two-day event that unites researchers, industry and developers to exchange knowledge and deployment of information systems for crisis management.	link
Natural Disaster Expo	4 times per year different continents September 2023	Event for mitigating the consequences of the world's most costly disasters: Heat & Fire, Earthquake, Flooding, storm.	link
The International Emergency Management Society (TIEMS)	Annual September 2023	TIEMS is a global forum for education, training and certification in emergency and disaster management.	link

Security Research Event (SRE)	Annual October 2023	The SRE is the annual meeting where industry, governments and knowledge institutions come together to discuss the state of play and current challenges for security research in Europe. The SRE also features a large exhibition area dedicated to the EU funded security-related projects.	link
INTERGEO	Annual October 2023	EXPO and CONFERENCE for geospatial solutions.	link
European Civil Protection Forum	Biannual Jun/July 2024	The Forum welcomes actors involved in the implementation and shaping of the European Civil Protection Policy. This includes representatives from the civil protection and disaster management communities such as governments, local, national and regional civil protection authorities, first responders, EU institutions, the scientific community and the private sector as well as other relevant stakeholders wishing to provide their input to this discussion.	link
Int. Crisis and Risk Communication Conference (ICRCC)	Annual TBD	ICRCC network crisis communication practitioners, leaders and researchers.	link
Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre (DRMKC)	Annual TBD	The European Commission Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre integrates existing scientific multi-disciplinary knowledge and co-develops innovative solutions for existing needs. Activities of the EC DRMKC support the translation of complex scientific data and analyses into usable information and provides science-based advice for DRM policies.	link
International Wildland Fire Conference (IWFC)	3-4 Years TBD	Conference to promote exchange of expertise and international cooperation in wildland fire management. These conferences have gathered thousands of participants around the world and are overseen by The International Liaison Committee (ILC), serving as an advisory and liaison body to the hosts of the conferences. The ILC recognizes that landscape fire management is an international issue, thus working closely with conference hosts and seeking new opportunities for sharing experiences in this area of knowledge.	link

Table 5 - List of potential events relevant for OVERWATCH

Copernicus Emergency Service events ([link](#)) will be monitored monthly. In this context, it must be highlighted that any other event related to emergency management solutions, floods and wildfires may be a proper venue to disseminate OVERWATCH results. Constant monitoring of those events will be performed and new events will be shared with consortium.

3.1.1.6. Trainings

In the frame of the project, task 4.3 “End-user training”, training for operational use and promotion of OVERWATCH tools and products will be organised in the implementation phase i.e., starting from M24 onwards.

Such trainings will be carried out to ensure that the target audience (end-users) will be updated with the visual appearance and functionalities of the system at the time of its use. An assessment of the learning requirements will be carried out and the appropriate training content will be developed for the introduction and generation of proficiency in the use of the system. This training is planned to be carried out in two distinct phases: the first contact and exploration of the mechanics of the system will be carried out in a back-office environment using e/b-learning or other methodologies such as applied gaming and simulation and a second phase carried out in the field with the system in full operation (task T4.4 “Field demonstration and feedback workshops”). The training will be designed according to the user’s needs.

3.1.1.7. Newsletters

In order to report the project’s achievements and technical developments, every 6 months a newsletter will be produced starting from the M6 and it is supposed to finish on the last project’s month M36.

The main aim of the newsletter is to inform about the project progress, events and relevant news. This will allow to establish the grounds for adoption of the OVERWATCH system and solutions in both the public and the private sectors, being a key platform for promoting the use and uptake.

Moreover, this marketing tool will be specifically addressed to potential end-users, governments and most importantly industry partners with potential interest in purchasing the OVERWATCH developed solutions. Moreover, citizens with particular interest for the topic can subscribe to this newsletter on the project’s website.

3.1.2. Dissemination for user and stakeholder involvement

Dissemination implies also the process of sharing information and knowledge with relevant stakeholders and users in different phases of the project and in relation to the different objectives and activities. In the context of user and stakeholder involvement, dissemination serves as a means of facilitating communication and collaboration between these groups and the project team. Dissemination strategies presented in the following chapters such as contact database (chapter 3.1.2.1), in-field demonstration and workshops (chapter 3.1.2.2) and clustering activities (chapter 3.1.2.3) ensure that information is communicated clearly and efficiently, and that stakeholders are engaged in the project.

3.1.2.1. Contact database

To assure end-users and stakeholder engagement and involvement within the OVERWATCH project various activities have been set in place starting from the very beginning. A contact database to identify and address the relevant target groups has been set up in order to collect inputs of key actors. Prior explicit consent, general information of these contacts (e.g., first and last name, e-mail contacts, organization/ company where they work, position covered in the organization/ company and related country) will be collected in the database. The database is hosted on the ALPHA server. Such information will be used for dissemination purposes only.

Given the foreseen applications of OVERWATCH, the focus will be on collection of contacts of organisations and professionals who have shown an interest in the project outcomes during the interaction, as their support will be essential in the creation and exploitation of the project results.

3.1.2.2. In-field demonstration and workshops

During the project lifetime the workshops will be held in two different moments: i) early stage of the project and ii) final stage of the project.

During the first project's months, a set of local workshops in Poland and Portugal, relative to the user's needs and requirements have been performed, the detailed report is provided in D1.1 [RD02]. These workshops aimed at collecting feedback from experts with very diverse profiles and previous experience, covering various thematic areas relevant for OVERWATCH. The criteria for selecting the groups of experts were: recognised expertise in emergency response, inclusive representation across different command tiers and open aptitude towards innovative technologies (e.g., communications technologies, earth observation, geographic information systems (GIS), drones, etc.). To make the participants feel comfortable and be more engaging, the workshops have been performed in their native language, Portuguese and Polish.

At the final project stage, two field demonstrations are foreseen and will be followed by workshops, Task 5.4 [RD01]. In such way they can provide an opportunity for end users and stakeholder to collect useful information in the frame of the cocreation process of the OVERWATCH tools but also represent an adequate venue in which results will be presented, feedbacks and possible improvements will be identified and discussed, a business session to discuss exploitation is also foreseen in [RD01]. To this aim, two in-field demonstrations, one for wildfire event and one for flood event, followed by workshops are foreseen in Portugal and Poland.

3.1.2.3. Clustering activities

As foreseen in [RD01], clustering activities with identified relevant networks will be promoted at European and local levels, in order to take advantage of the existing initiatives joined by OVERWATCH consortium partners (see Table 6).

Area of influence	Name	Description
Europe	European Network of Defence-related Regions ENDR	ENDR brings together regional authorities and clusters to share experiences and best practices on dual use and defence-related activities. <i>ALPHA is managing and maintaining the ENDR website.</i>
Europe	Crisis Management Innovation Network Europe CMINE	CMINE is the hub for crisis management professionals in the EU and beyond. It aims to foster innovation and research uptake in crisis management through cross-sector, multi-stakeholder dialogues around capability gaps and potential solutions. <i>CIK CBK, ENG and LINKS are members of the network.</i>
Europe	Community for European Research and Innovation for Security CERIS	CERIS that facilitate interactions within the security research community and users of research outputs. <i>CIK CBK, ENG, LINKS and INESC TEC are members of the community.</i>

Europe	European Association of Remote Sensing Companies EARSC	EARSC is a membership-based, not for profit organisation which coordinates and promotes the activities of European companies engaged in delivering Earth observation-derived geo-information services. EARSC creates a network between industry, decision makers and users covering the full EO value chain from data acquisition through processing, fusion, analysis to final geo-information products & services. <i>ITHACA is a full member of the EARSC.</i>
Europe	Copernicus Relays Network	The European Commission has established in 2017 a network of Copernicus ambassadors: the Copernicus Relays . They act as local champions, coordinating and promoting activities around the Copernicus Programme, promoting its opportunities and benefits of the EU's Earth Observation Programme to the local citizens and businesses. <i>ITHACA is a Copernicus ambassador.</i>
National	Crisis Information Centre CIK CBK	CIK unites knowhow of science development and end-user's view. Part of the space Research Centre of Polish Academy of Sciences. The main aim of CIK activities is to increase effectiveness in the field of rescue and crisis management. <i>CIK CBK is a project partner.</i>

Table 6 - Cluster networks relevant to OVERWATCH

As stated in [RD01], OVERWATCH will explore the possibility for links creation with end-users networks and clusters such as Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network, Crisis Management Innovation Network Europe, Community for European Research and Innovation for Security, EFFIS/GWIS, EFAS/GLOFDAS, prioritizing these direct access channels to end-users and field operatives but also with other Copernicus and EGNOS initiatives and existing services such as Forest Information System for Europe, Global Wildfire Information System, European Forest Fire Information System in terms of collaboration, improvement and expansion of services.

3.2. Exploitation of results

The consortium expects to commercialise OVERWATCH project's results firstly in Europe and then beyond once the tools demonstrate their advantages competitive with the worldwide concurrent. In this direction, the exploitation plan will leverage on key results of the project to define a detailed action plan to enter the market (including identification of the right value proposition, the key activities to undertake, the KPIs to measure, etc.).

It is important to mention that the objective of defining the exploitation activities in this deliverable is to recap on what is planned for the market uptake of the proposed solutions. It is useful to have a clear overview on the overall promotion system, which certainly includes exploitation activities.

The content of the exploitation activity will be focused on the exploitation plan, reporting on the results of the business assessment tasks carried out during the project in order to support the commercial exploitation of the project results at European scale. Task, T5.4 "Exploitation of project results" has, among its objective, the creation of the exploitation plan and kick-off of the activities based on an exploitation plan to disseminate and exploit the project results. The main activity

foreseen is the project exploitation (chapter 3.2.1); however, other activities are also expected and furthermore presented, such as the interface with similar and new projects and with main European Institutions (chapter 3.2.2).

3.2.1. Project exploitation

To guarantee the transfer of project results beyond its life, an all-inclusive exploitation strategy is planned for the end of the project.

The exploitation of project results, “Exploitation plan and first exploitation activities” (D5.5, to be delivered in M36) will form the basis for further development of the project’s outputs and will include measures to ensure that the benefits of the project will endure beyond its lifetime. It is important to mention, where applicable patent initiative will be evaluated together with the partners.

3.2.2. Similar and new projects monitoring and interface

OVERWATCH aims to leverage on the experience from similar and complementary EU-funded projects. Thus, through different venues the members of the consortium have established contacts with project coordinators in order to establish collaborations and share knowledge and experiences. In addition, a database of relevant EU projects for OVERWATCH is presented in Table 7.

Name	Description	Foreseen Interaction
CHRIS	Critical infrastructure High accuracy and Robustness increase Integrated Synchronization Solutions project will detect and mitigate radio interferences, jamming and spoofing attacks on telecommunication networks. A Galileo-based timing distribution and synchronisation solution will increase resilience to GNSS signals interference, jamming, spoofing and cyberattacks on the fibre-optics distribution layer.	OVERWATCH, CHRIS and EWOKS share the same call and some of the objectives overlap. In order to leverage on the high concentration of talent (nearly 25 partners between all three projects), fluent communication will be established.
EWOKS	Enabling Emergency warning service/galileo Market Uptake in widespread PWS Solutions project will develop GNSS, equipment to receive and process the EWS messages.	
Firelogue	European project, funded by Horizon 2020 under the Green Deal call, that brings together expertise from all around Europe when it comes to Wildfire Risk Management.	Communication will be established to join the Wild Fire Risk Management community and create a synergy with one or more projects.
EU Fire projects United	Project that aims to accelerate cross-disciplinary communication between fire scientists, with the overall goal to provide for policy makers and land users strong, research-lead foundations that enable implementation of more effective land management approaches.	Communication will be established to join the EU fire project united community and create a synergy with one or more projects.

<p>Trusted Extremely Precise Mapping and Prediction for Emergency Management TEMA</p>	<p>TEMA will develop an integrated, ground-breaking Natural Disasters Management platform, focusing on real-time semantic extraction from multiple heterogeneous data modalities and sources, on-the-fly construction of a meaningful semantically annotated 3D disaster area map, prediction of disaster evolution and improved communication between service providers and end-users, through automated process triggering and response recommendations. The proposed service will be validated on two disaster use-cases (wildfire and floods).</p>	<p>TEMA project has some objectives in common with OVERWATCH. Communication will be established to seek for potential synergies.</p>
<p>HARMONIA</p>	<p>Development of a Support System, named IRAP for Improved Resilience and Sustainable Urban areas to cope with Climate Change and Extreme Events based on GEOSS and Advanced Modelling Tools.</p>	<p>Communication will be established to seek for potential synergies.</p>

Table 7 - OVERWATCH similar project database (preliminary)

3.2.2.1. Synergies

OVERWATCH will search for synergies in the EGNOS initiatives and H2020/HE projects (potential projects of interest have been mapped in Table 7). Moreover, there is a dedicated Task 5.3 “International cooperation and synergies” which as the main objectives has building synergies with ongoing EU and international projects, civil protection networks and other initiatives of interest inside the sector. For example, joint dissemination and possible synergies to support the technologic evolution are some of the potential actions to increase the value and performance of the project.

3.3. Communication

As explained in section 2.2, communication has the strategic value of providing the basis for and supporting potential-users engagement, especially in the co-creation process of the project. Moreover, communication is also understood as a fundamental support to convince key target groups of the societal and economic benefits generated by OVERWATCH. Therefore to promote the project towards all stakeholders, end-users and to scientific community, the further actions are planned and presented in the following chapters: exploitation of the website for other promotion activities (chapter 3.3.1), development of the audio-visual material (chapter 3.3.2) social media publications (chapter 3.3.3) and other communication channels (chapter 3.3.4).

3.3.1. Exploitation of the website for other promotion activities

The OVERWATCH website could be leveraged as a tool not only for project dissemination, but also for project promotion, for example through the:

- Websites cross-linking to exchange site links and increase Google rank/positioning, providing a mutual advantage to both the OVERWATCH and the partners’ websites.
- Publication on the OVERWATCH website of external press releases that are relevant to the project and/ or the work of the consortium members.
- Website ads campaigns: OVERWATCH banner could be shown on related websites.

3.3.2. Development of audio-visual materials

Audio-visual material can be a powerful tool for dissemination, as it combines two sensory inputs (audio and visual) to create a more engaging and impactful experience for the viewer or listener. This type of dissemination actions can cover different topics and events of the project (e.g., animation video, interview and presentation of participating institutions, coverage of in-field demonstrations etc).

First introductory project [video](#) has been created and published together with the website. The idea behind this dissemination material is to explain in a short and simple way the project and foster the interest of the people inside and outside the sector.

Future materials will have focus on results communication and demonstration of the project activities. It is important to point out that gender-neutral and gender-sensitive content is predefined during the material creation.

3.3.3. Social media publications

In order to achieve general communication of the project, some key social media channels have been identified to ensure that activities and achievements of the projects are publicized and broadcasted in various formats and to different audience.

OVERWATCH account has been created in the following social media platforms:

Social media platform	OVERWATCH profile	Audience
Facebook	link	General public
Twitter	link	General public
YouTube	link	General public
LinkedIn	link	Researchers and professionals
Research Gate	Could be leveraged by the activity of the project researchers	Researchers and professionals

Table 8 - OVERWATCH Social Media channels

Having the profiles set up, the following social media strategy has been defined outlining the goals, messaging, and tactics to be used on each platform. The proposed social media strategy applies to Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn as a platform where frequent content posting is planned. Generally speaking, the content will cover the latest activities, workshops and trainings organized, events attended, publications and results achieved. Though different content is planned for different social media platform, to diversify the channels and keep audience engaged. By tailoring the content to each platform, it is possible to maximize the reach. The content will be shared at least once per week per platform on different days and time. Different “tone of voice” will be used for different platforms as presented in the Table 9.

Social media platform	Tone of voice
Facebook	Narrative, authentic.
Twitter	Brief, clear and use simple language.
LinkedIn	Scientific approach, long text with a focus on technical issues.

Table 9 - OVERWATCH tone of voice for social media platforms

Generally speaking, “the tone of voice² used will reflect the OVERWATCH project values and encourages conversation with and engagement of the audience. The gender-neutral and gender-sensitive content is predefined during the social media publications (see chapter 3.4). The everyday

activity will provide short time responses to comments and feedback and engaging with the audience in a positive and constructive manner.

To enrich the content and the reach, posts dedicated to the international days relevant to the project will be shared on Facebook and Twitter. Columns with an insights and partners interview are also planned to be published once per month.

Moreover, in view of the utilisation of social media channels, some suggestions on the main hashtags and key words to be used are shared with the OVERWATCH partners. In this context, it must be highlighted that a proper use of hashtags will help increase OVERWATCH social media presence as they make the content viewable by anyone who has an interest in the proposed hashtag as it goes beyond just the followers of OVERWATCH. These are the following:

#AI #DRONES #AUGMENTEDREALITY #AR #DISASTERRESPONSE #DISASTERMANAGEMENT #EMERGENCYMANAGEMENT #CRISIS #EARTH OBSERVATION #EO #EGNSS #OVERWATCH #OVERWATCHproject #HORIZONEU #EUproject #EUSpace #EUSPA

Tagging consortium partners and EUSPA could increase the reach and foster the networking as well. Nevertheless, all Consortium partners are invited to share OVERWATCH project development and results to their own communication office in order to maximise the reach of the communication activities.

3.3.4. Other communication channels

The project will be communicated to the public also at large scale using other communication channels e.g., via press releases and participation in radio, newspapers, magazines at local and regional level. The content will cover general information, latest news and OVERWATCH features.

3.4. Gender issues in project dissemination and communication activities

Gender issues in European project dissemination and communication activities are a complex and multifaceted problem that requires a comprehensive approach to overcome. The EU has made significant progress in promoting gender equality in various fields, including research and innovation. However, gender inequalities still persist in project dissemination and communication activities, which can negatively impact the effectiveness of these activities.

One of the significant challenges in overcoming gender issues in project dissemination and communication is the persistent gender stereotypes and biases that exist in society. These biases can affect the language, visuals, and messaging used in project dissemination and communication, leading to the perpetuation of gender stereotypes and biases. To overcome such biases, in OVERWATCH, we follow the “gendered innovation” approach, defined by the EC by integrating the sex and gender perspective in the knowledge generation and the development of the strategies and guidelines and by considering the differential impacts of the actions developed on different population groups including men and women.

When it comes to the dissemination and communication activities, to make sure that all processes are inclusive, a specific action plan with main procedures have been set in place in order to address possible gender issue(s). In carrying out the activities we specifically pay attention to:

- Gender-neutral / sensitive wording:
 - Gender-impartial language is implemented in the communication and dissemination activities. Our messages are structured to possibly avoid any bias towards a particular sex or social gender.

- When reporting informative data, this is reported in a gender-sensitive way.
- Gender-neutral images:
 - As images can speak louder than words, we are attentive in selecting appealing images (especially for communication purposes). This means that the images use in our communication materials does not reinforce gender stereotypes and includes a wide mix of people in different environments.

Once both these criteria are met, the dissemination and communication processes are allowed to move forward.

Additionally, it is worth to note that, any gender specific results such as gender sensitive policies that provide visibility for the inclusion of gender perspective into research and projects results, will be specifically disseminated and highlighted.

Moreover, as per DoA [RD01], the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), overviews all project activities under the Responsible Research and Innovation' key aspects - that are extremely relevant in OVERWATCH - (i.e., Ethics, Gender Equality, Governance, Open access, Science Education, Stakeholder engagement). The RRI's overview combined with the specific action plan in terms of communication and dissemination, allows to ensure that all the documents developed within the OVERWATCH project guarantee that the gender dimension is integrated as a transversal issue in the project activities.

In conclusion, overcoming gender issues in project dissemination and communication activities requires a comprehensive approach that addresses gender stereotypes and biases, promotes gender-sensitive language and visuals, and evaluates project dissemination and communication activities from a gender perspective.

By taking these steps, we can create more inclusive and effective activities that promote gender equality and advance the EU's goals of innovation and sustainability.

4. Conclusions and expected results

This document has illustrated the plan for the dissemination, exploitation and communication in the context of the OVERWATCH project, both covering activities already performed during the first months and those planned for the rest of the project. The majority of these activities have been already presented in [RD01], in particular in WP5 "Dissemination Communication & Exploitation".

As seen, the main focus of OVERWATCH promotion is dissemination, which forms the basis of the overall strategy. This is due to the fact that the innovative solution proposed by OVERWATCH and the final product resulting from R&D are not widely known to most U&S. The key channels for dissemination are the website and the participation in international conferences and events. If relevant and feasible, specific communication activities will be implemented to reach a wider audience. However, these actions are of secondary importance in the overall OVERWATCH promotion plan, as the project primarily targets professionals rather than the mass market audience.

It is to be noted that for all these activities, gender-neutral and gender-sensitive language is utilised and a specific action plan related to communication and dissemination has been set in place. This allows to ensure that the gender dimension is integrated as a transversal issue in the OVERWATCH project activities.

Finally, about the dissemination, exploitation and communication tools and materials suggested in the previous sections, the expected results are summarised in Table 10, in terms of goals and key performance indicators (KPIs).

Item	Goal	Quantity	KPI
Logo	Diffusion to the widest audience	1	Logo ready
Website	Create a user-friendly website	1	50 000+ visits updated regularly
Project brochure	To reach large audience	2+	200+ readers
Press references	Diffusion to widest audience by general non-scientific means by Consortium	20+	1 000+ readers
Short video	Short video explaining key research outputs	10	5 000+ views
Demonstration video	Videos from demonstration	2	
Final video	Final video of the project with an overview of the product and results obtained	1	
International conferences and events	Participation to a key event and publication to peer-reviewed scientific journals	3+ presentations 5 journals 10 conference papers	200+ people per event
Trainings	Trainings for professionals during the project, mostly linked with technical application works performed at the case studies	2+	150 people
Newsletter	Engagement with target groups	6	1 every 6 months
Contact Database	Key Contact database	1	Updated regularly
Demonstration	Demonstration with advisory group, stakeholders and first responders	2 events In 2 different countries	25 + organisations involved
Clustering activities	Promotion of networks and active cluster with other H2020 European ongoing related projects, European and National Technology Platforms (e.g., CERIS)	3+	3+ EU organizations, clusters or working groups engaged for user needs definition and results dissemination
Synergies	Increase value and performance of the project (e.g., joint dissemination and synergy to support the technological evolution)	2+ 2+	2+ EGNOS initiatives 2+ H2020/HE projects
Social media	Spreading the project achievements to a wider audience	3 accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook) 300+ posts	5 000+ followers 10 000+ interactions

Table 10 - OVERWATCH dissemination and communication tools and expected results

References

ID	Title	Access Date
[RD01]	OVERWATCH Grant agreement No. 101082320	2023
[RD02]	D 1.1 End-users requirements	2023
[RD03]	EC Funding & tender opportunities SEDIA: what is the difference between dissemination, exploitation and communication, link	2023